

LOCALITY

Circularity Powered by Algae

Consumer Acceptance of Algae-Based Foods

White Paper

Publish Date: 15 October 2025

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Technical References

Project Acronym	LOCALITY
Project Title	Nature-positive aLgae-based fOod, agriculture, AquacuLture and textile productS made in North and Baltic Sea ecosYstems
Project Coordinator	Margarida Costa
Project Duration	2023–2027

Deliverable No.	
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Work Package	8
Task	8.5
Lead beneficiary	Umeå University
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	NIVA, ESCI
Due date of deliverable	M7-M48
Actual submission date	

- 1 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Summary

It is widely recognised that the global food system must undergo a significant transformation in response to the climate emergency. The systems supporting meat consumption alone are responsible for nearly a fifth of greenhouse gases produced today, and the incidence of diet-related, non-communicable diseases is rising (Romanello et al., 2024). Among the strategies proposed to mitigate the environmental and health impacts of animal-based foods is the development of alternative proteins, including plant-based products derived from algae. With their promising nutritional profiles, rapid growth rate, and relatively low environmental footprint, algae represent a valuable source of protein that could support a sustainable and healthy dietary transition in Europe (Wells et al., 2016). However, they remain underutilised in mainstream food systems. Their potential role in advancing sustainable diets and food security largely depends on consumer acceptance. Therefore, to better understand consumer acceptance and perceptions of algae-based foods, researchers at Umeå University conducted a cross-national survey of 5,250 individuals across seven Northern and Eastern European countries (Sweden, Germany, Finland, Estonia, Lithuania, Norway, and Poland) in the frame of the Task 8.5 (Consumer acceptance) of the European project LOCALITY . The study aimed to investigate behavioural patterns, preferences, and attitudes towards algae-based foods, and the potential of these foods to contribute to sustainable dietary transitions.

Summary of Dietary Lifestyle Results

The LOCALITY survey findings reveal diverse dietary patterns among Northern and Eastern European consumers, including omnivores, flexitarians, vegetarians, vegans, and pescatarians. The majority has been identified as omnivores (over 60%), with flexitarians forming the second-largest group. In Germany, flexitarians represent the largest consumer group (49%), surpassing omnivores. Pescatarians, vegetarians, and vegans represented a small minority among consumers (<10%). This distribution reflects a population that is still largely reliant on traditional diets based on the consumption of animal-based foods, with limited but growing interest in reduced meat consumption.

Summary of Consumption and Change Results

Despite most EU member states' nutritional recommendations to reduce consumption of meat and other animal-based foods, they constitute a large part of most respondents' diets; however, there is clear momentum towards reducing this. Approximately 27% of the participants reported an intention to reduce their intake of meat products within the next six months, followed by lower – but still significant – intentions to reduce dairy consumption. While dairy products continue to be widely consumed, as observed in other European surveys, a noticeable proportion of respondents indicated a behavioural change or intention to change towards more plant-based consumption. These findings suggest that an early but promising consumer openness to alternative proteins, particularly in terms of health and sustainability, is emerging in the surveyed countries. Despite this, algae-based foods remain largely unfamiliar and under-consumed, with most consumers having little or no prior experience with them. Therefore, algae-based foods currently have a low market penetration, suggesting their potential to grow in terms of market share.

Summary of Perceptions, Motives, and Barriers Results

While sustainability and health are recognised as important, taste remains the primary motive guiding food choices among Northern and Eastern European consumers. The respondents consistently ranked pleasurable sensations (such as taste and texture) and affordability as their top reasons for food selection, with environmental and ethical concerns secondary. Despite a generally favourable perspective on the potential of algae-based foods, significant perceptual barriers to their consumption persist. The most reported include a lack of familiarity, and concerns about taste and texture. Additionally, perceived low availability and higher cost further discourage consumers.

Summary of Market Opportunities Results

Market opportunities for algae-based foods are emerging but require strategic positioning. Most (57%) respondents were moderately willing to try algae-based foods, especially when these are incorporated into familiar food formats such as meat alternatives. However, this interest was highly contingent on the quantity of algae in the options: consumers preferred products with low algae content, with acceptance peaking at 10% inclusion and decreasing sharply beyond that threshold. This suggests that algae should initially be used as a complementary ingredient rather than the main one. Additionally, the respondents favour products that are affordable, accessible, and sensorially similar to those animal-based foods that they are meant to replace. These insights highlight a cautious yet promising market environment for algae-based foods, particularly when aligned with consumer expectations regarding taste, pricing, and ease of integration into existing eating habits.

Summary of Trust in Algae-Based Foods

Trust in algae-based foods remains moderate and highly regionally dependent, with clear differences across the seven surveyed Northern and Eastern European countries. Respondents from countries such as Norway and Germany exhibited higher levels of trust, while Lithuanians expressed more scepticism. Across all countries, trust was closely linked to familiarity and transparency; consumers were more likely to trust algae-based foods when they understood their origins and production methods, and the health benefits associated with them. These findings emphasise that building consumer trust will be essential for promoting algae-based foods, and that efforts should focus on education, sensory trials, and transparent communication.

Summary of Sensory Preferences Results

Sensory characteristics, in terms of appearance, odour, taste/flavour, and texture/mouthfeel, were evaluated for algae-based alternatives to egg, meat, and fish. Algae-based fish alternatives were viewed favourably, with the respondents expressing preferences for fresh, marine, and salty flavours, soft and crisp textures, and bright appearance, likely due to natural associations with aquatic products. In contrast, algae-based egg alternatives received the lowest sensory approval, with clear preferences for an eggy taste, tenderness, light yellow colour, and creamy or roasted aromas, while matcha/green notes, fluid textures, and foamy visuals were strongly rejected. Algae-based meat alternatives were also positively perceived when offering beef-like taste, brown appearance, uniform tenderness, and a meaty aroma, while green hues and vegetable-like flavours were viewed negatively. Texture remained a key concern across all products, with consumers hesitating in response to slimy, fatty, or overly marine sensations. These findings underscore that successful algae-based foods must prioritise appealing, familiar sensory profiles to foster consumer acceptance.

Conclusion

This study offers valuable insights into the evolving attitudes of Northern and Eastern European consumers to algae-based foods. While overall familiarity remains low, there is evident openness to trying algae-based foods, particularly when they are integrated into familiar food formats and at modest inclusion levels. Taste, availability, and ease of preparation are key drivers of acceptance, while cost and lack of familiarity remain the main barriers. Importantly, consumers value algae for their sustainability and health potential, aligning well with broader societal goals for more sustainable diets. These findings point to a promising opportunity for algae-based foods. If introduced gradually, supported by clear communication, and designed with consumer sensory expectations in mind, algae can become a meaningful part of Europe's future alternative protein landscape.

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1 The Need for a Sustainable and Healthy Food Transition

The global demand for protein is rapidly increasing due to population growth, rising incomes, and shifting dietary behaviours (Yadav et al., 2025). The global population is expected to grow significantly, such that by 2050, a projected 70% increase in food production compared to current levels will be required to meet demand (Walter et al., 2022). However, traditional protein sources—particularly those of animal origin—pose serious environmental and health-related challenges. The intensive production and consumption of animal-based foods are associated with high greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, land degradation, biodiversity loss, excessive freshwater use, and widespread environmental pollution (Poore & Nemecek, 2018; IPCC, 2023). From a public-health perspective, diets high in animal-sourced foods (ASFs) have been linked to a greater risk of chronic non-communicable diseases (NCDs), including cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and obesity, highlighting the need for both prevention and improved disease management (Springmann et al., 2018). To address these interconnected crises – climate change, environmental degradation, and the rising global burden of NCDs – there is an urgent need for systemic changes in global food systems. A key strategy involves shifting towards more sustainable, plant-based dietary patterns, away from the production and consumption of animal-based foods (Poore et al., 2018). This transition is widely recognised as being essential to achieving planetary health and ensuring long-term food security (IPCC, 2023).

1.1 Why Algae?

In this scenario, algae emerge as a promising and more sustainable alternative to challenges relating to global food security and the environment. Algae, particularly microalgae, are alternative protein sources that can be applied in innovative ways due to their biochemical content, rapid growth rates, and capacity to grow in non-arable land and nutrient-rich sidestreams systems, reducing competition with food crops for freshwater and land use (Tahir et al., 2024). Microalgae are a rich source of high-quality proteins and contain all the essential amino acids. Genera such as *Spirulina* and *Chlorella* include species with protein contents of 50–70% and 40–60%, respectively, comparable to or exceeding those of conventional animal and plant protein sources, including meat and soy (Ma et al., 2024). Additionally, microalgae are rich in vitamins, minerals, and bioactive compounds, enhancing their nutritional profile and providing different health-related functionalities (Ma et al., 2024). Furthermore, microalgae play an active role in carbon consumption, utilising CO₂ during photosynthesis and enabling integration with industrial systems to mitigate GHG emissions (Daneshvar et al., 2022).

Given their positive impact on human health and the environment, microalgae are currently considered key ingredients in developing products that mimic ASFs, such as meat, fish, and eggs. Their wide variety of textures and flavour profiles, along with their dense nutritional content, make them particularly suitable for plant-based foods. Still, their potential success largely depends on consumers' willingness and ability to change their food behaviour towards them. Therefore, understanding acceptance of algae-based foods by women and men is crucial for successful market integration.

1.2 The Role of Algae-Based Foods in Europe's Dietary Transition

Gaining insights into how people respond to ASF analogues that contain algae is crucial to advancing a sustainable and healthy food transition in Europe. While most EU member states' dietary guidelines highlight the importance of reducing meat consumption and increasing intake of plant-based foods, empirical evidence reveals that many EU citizens do not align their dietary behaviours with nutritional recommendations, highlighting an alarming gap between nutritional guidance and actual practices (SmartProtein, 2021; HealthFerm, 2024). This disconnection exists despite the implementation at the European level of major policy frameworks, such as the European Green

Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy, which aimed to foster more sustainable and healthy food systems (von Philipsborn et al., 2022). Achieving a sustainable and healthy food system in Europe requires coordinated efforts and shared responsibility among all actors across the food system. Additionally, providing strategic, evidence-based actions is key to supporting the transition towards more sustainable production and consumption patterns (Willet et al., 2019). In this context, the Horizon Europe programme plays a key role in funding research and innovation to accelerate the development and accessibility of alternative protein sources such as algae, which contribute to both environmental sustainability and improved public health. As part of this initiative, the EU-funded LOCALITY project contributes to the broader transformation of the food system by providing strategic data on consumer attitudes, acceptance, and perceived barriers related to algae-based foods. In doing so, LOCALITY addresses the underexplored yet promising role of algae in enabling a sustainable and healthy food transition in Europe.

2 Overview of Consumer Profiles in Northern and Eastern EU Countries

This study was conducted by researchers at Umeå University as part of Task 8.5 of the LOCALITY project, which investigates consumer acceptance of algae-based foods in seven Northern and Eastern EU countries (SE, DE, FI, EE, LT, NO, PL). The choice of countries included in the study reflects the geographical scope of the Horizon Europe (HORIZON) call, which emphasises the development of innovative, sustainable algae-based value chains in the Baltic and North Sea regions. Data were collected through an online survey from November to December 2024. The market research agency Enkätfabriken AB carried out the survey via the Cint panel.

2.1 Socio-Demographic and Household Profile Characteristics

The survey sample consisted of a total of 5,250 respondents from these seven Northern and Eastern EU countries, comprising a gender-balanced sample: 50% of the respondents identified as women, 49.8% as men, and 0.2% as "Other/Prefer not to say". In terms of residential distribution (illustrated in Figure 1), most respondents (64%) lived in urban areas, followed by 20% who lived in rural areas, and 17% residing in suburban areas. The participants were also asked to evaluate their household's financial situation. Figure 2 shows that most respondents (39%) rated their economic situation as "neutral," while 32% perceived it as "difficult" and around 30% as "easy." These assessments are based on self-reported perceptions, using a scale that ranged from "extremely difficult" to "extremely easy". These findings highlight how, despite the sample mainly being from Northern EU countries – generally associated with higher average incomes and robust welfare systems – a notable proportion of people live in difficult financial situations, underscoring the presence of vulnerable population segments.

Figure 1: Response to where interviewees live, distributed in urban, suburban and rural.

Figure 2: Responses on the financial situation of the interviewees.

Regarding the education level of the sample (Figure 3), the majority of respondents (27%) had completed secondary school as their highest level of education, and 25% had finished undergraduate studies as their highest level of education. Only a small percentage (5%) had completed primary school as their highest level of education.

Figure 3: Distribution of the highest level of education the interviewees have.

Respondents in the seven sampled EU countries reported varying household sizes (Figure 4), with the largest group being those living in two-person households (36%), followed by single-person households (25%). Larger households with five or more members were rare (5%). This distribution reflects the demographic trend in Northern and Eastern Europe towards smaller household units, particularly in urban and ageing populations. When asked about the presence of children in their households (Figure 5), most respondents (40%) reported not having children, while nearly 30% reported having one child.

Figure 4: Distribution of household members of the interviewees.

Figure 5: Distribution of numbers of children per household.

2.2 Respondent Health

The respondents were asked to self-rate their overall health, based on their personal perception, using a scale ranging from “very bad” to “very good.”. As shown in Figure 6, approximately 90% perceived themselves as

generally healthy, with only a small portion indicating a poor health status. Despite this notable healthy perception, the number of respondents having received a medical diagnosis (Figure 7) was relatively high, at approximately 50%. Of that group, most had been diagnosed with high blood pressure (57%), followed by high cholesterol (42%). The data reveal an apparent discrepancy between self-perceived health and medical diagnoses among respondents, showing that many individuals may underestimate their health risks or consider these conditions manageable and compatible with a healthy lifestyle.

Figure 6: Responses to the health in general of the interviewees.

Figure 7: Replies if the interviewees are suffering from any of the indicated illnesses.

3 Consumer Behaviours Regarding Plant-Based Eating

The respondents were asked to provide information on their dietary lifestyles. To ensure consistency in responses, they were first presented with clear definitions of each lifestyle, as follows:

- **Omnivore:** "I frequently eat meat such as beef, pork, chicken, turkey, fish, and/or shellfish."
- **Flexitarian:** "I sometimes eat meat, but I am trying to reduce my meat consumption and often choose plant-based foods."
- **Pescatarian:** "I eat fish and/or shellfish, but no other types of meat."
- **Vegetarian:** "I don't eat meat and fish of any kind, but I do eat eggs and/or dairy products."
- **Vegan:** "I don't eat meat, fish, eggs, dairy products, nor any other animal-based ingredients."

Figure 8 shows how, among the 5,250 respondents from the seven sampled Northern and Eastern EU countries, the majority identified as omnivores (68%), followed by flexitarians (26%). Smaller proportions identified as vegetarian (3%), pescatarian (3%), and vegan (1%). Country-level analysis reveals meaningful variation. In Germany, flexitarians constituted the largest group (49%), surpassing omnivores, indicating dietary transition in that context and confirming trends highlighted by other European projects. In contrast, Finland and Estonia exhibited the highest proportions of omnivores, with rates exceeding 70%, and notably low numbers of vegetarians and vegans (less than 5%). The percentage of pescatarians, vegetarians, and vegans remains steadily low in all of the sampled countries. These results confirm that while omnivorous diets remain dominant across Northern and Eastern Europe, certain countries, notably Germany, are experiencing a visible shift towards emerging sustainability-oriented dietary patterns such as flexitarianism.

Figure 8: Responses of the interviewees on their dietary lifestyle.

Additionally, the respondents were asked to provide insights into the duration of adherence to their current dietary lifestyles (Figure 9). Approximately half of the sample (53%) reported following their current dietary lifestyle since birth, and only 6% had adopted their current dietary lifestyle within the past six months, indicating that recent diet shifts were relatively uncommon in this sample. When examining motivations for dietary change (Figure 10), personal health emerged as the main reason, reported by approximately 39% of respondents. This was followed by taste preference (19%) and, to a lesser extent, animal welfare (12%) and environmental sustainability (7%). Social, economic, and cultural factors were less commonly mentioned. These

findings suggest that health and sensory appeal are more influential than ethical and environmental factors in driving dietary change. Regarding dietary transition (Figure 11), most of the participants who had changed their diets reported previously adhering to an omnivorous diet (61%), followed by a flexitarian diet (21%).

Figure 9: Responses on how long have the interviewees have followed their current dietary lifestyle.

Figure 10: Responses to the question “What diet did you switch from?”.

Figure 11: Replies on the main reason why they switched their diet.

4 Frequency of Consumption

When asked how frequently they consume different food groups (Figures 12 and 13), including animal and plant-based foods, the respondents reported that they consumed dairy products the most frequently, with a substantial proportion (approximately 47%) reporting daily or several times per week intake. Vegetables and fruits were the second most consumed food groups, with 29% and 25% of respondents reporting daily intake, respectively, followed by vegetable oils at 20%. Meat products, including processed meats, red meat, poultry, fish, and seafood, remain staples in the diets of many respondents. Between 30% and 40% of the sample reported consuming these 1–3 times per week, which significantly exceeds the intake recommended by most EU member states' dietary guidelines, pointing to an important public-health concern.

Meanwhile, plant-based meat and dairy alternatives were the least frequently consumed foods in the plant-based categories. Most respondents reported only occasional or no consumption of such foods. A similar trend was observed for micro- and macroalgae consumption, with 49% of respondents reporting having never consumed algae-based foods. To improve the uptake of ASF alternatives – such as the algae-based foods designed by the LOCALITY project – enhanced communication strategies that raise awareness and promote the benefits of these products are key to facilitating consumer acceptance.

Figure 12: Responses on the frequency of consumption of different animal-based foods.

Figure 13: Responses to the frequency of consuming different kinds of plant-based foods.

4.1 Dietary Change

When asked about any intended changes in consumption in both meat and dairy products over the next six months (Figure 14), most of the respondents from the seven Northern EU countries reported that they intended to keep the same level of consumption of dairy and meat products, respectively 72% and 63%, suggesting a relative stability of current dietary habits, particularly for dairy, which remains deeply integrated in daily consumption patterns. However, it is noteworthy that nearly 30% of respondents indicated that they intended to consume fewer meat products, suggesting a growing awareness of the health and environmental concerns related to these foods among EU consumers.

Figure 14: Responses for future consumption intentions in the next six months.

4.2 Food Choice Motives

Figure 15 shows that the two most prominent food choice motives reported were pleasurable sensations and affordability, indicating that respondents prioritise tasty foods, and that price is an important determinant of food choice. Convenience, in terms of buying and preparation, and healthiness were also rated highly (with a mean score of ~5.44), highlighting that the respondents choose their foods based on nutrition and ease of finding and cooking. In contrast, motives such as ethical concern, environmental sustainability, and weight control received lower preference, suggesting that while these factors are present in the consumer consciousness, they are less influential in everyday food choices.

Figure 15: Replies about the day-to-day food preferences of the interviewees.

4.3 Respondent’s Values

The Short Schwartz Values Scale was used to measure values among the respondents from the seven Northern EU countries (Figure 16). *Security*, *Benevolence*, and *Self-Direction* scored the highest, each receiving a mean score of approximately 6.0 or higher. These values reflect a general orientation towards the need for safety and stability, caring for others, and personal freedom. In contrast, values such as power and personal achievement scored notably lower, with mean scores of around 4.0–4.9, indicating that status-seeking and authority were less central to most respondents.

Figure 16: Responses to the question about the main values for the participants.

4.4 Attitudes to Plant-Based Eating

When asked to evaluate a series of statements regarding general attitudes to plant-based eating (Figure 17), the respondents expressed positive attitudes toward plant-based foods. A slight majority – approximately 51% – agreed that plant-based foods facilitate a sustainable and healthy dietary transition. Additionally, 48% of respondents felt that it would be easy to include more plant-based foods in their diets, and considered them to be nutritionally sufficient, challenging the common perception that plant-based diets may lack essential nutrients.

However, this positivity towards plant-based foods was offset by a key aspect that is of concern to many consumers: price. Thirty-six percent perceived plant-based foods as unaffordable, congruent with the food choice motives discussed above, and reflecting a significant barrier to broader adoption. Without addressing these economic constraints, the transition towards more sustainable diets risks being limited to higher-income individuals, thereby reinforcing dietary inequalities.

Figure 17: Responses on the attitudes towards plant-based foods in the 7 EU countries.

5 Consumer Attitudes to Algae-Based Foods

5.1 Familiarity with algae and algae-based foods

The respondents from the seven Northern and Eastern EU countries were asked to evaluate their attitudes to algae and algae-based foods. These foods, commonly referred to as "plant-based alternatives", are made using micro- and/or macroalgae biomasses, and are intended to resemble conventional animal-based foods such as meat or fish. The respondents were first asked to evaluate their general familiarity with microalgae (Figure 18); most (approximately 70%) did not recognise the names of the microalgae used to produce food alternatives, namely White *Chlorella*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, Honey *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Spirulina*, and *Tetraselmis chuii*. This overall low familiarity with algae among European consumers highlights a significant barrier to consumer acceptance but also presents a valuable opportunity for market development. Strategic interventions in education, targeted marketing, product development, and communication could help to normalise algae-based ingredients and possibly overcome consumer barriers.

Figure 18: Responses to the question on the level of familiarity with the different algae species.

Despite their low level of familiarity with most microalgae (Figure 19), around 52% of respondents reported that they are curious to try new foods containing algae, and 45% would like to incorporate these innovative foods into their regular diets. This highlights the potential for increasing acceptance, particularly among health-conscious and sustainability-oriented consumer segments.

Figure 19: Responses on the intentions towards the future consumption of algae-based foods in the 7 EU countries.

The respondents were also asked to evaluate the following statement about algae-based foods (Figure 20): "Algae-based foods facilitate a sustainable and healthy dietary transition." Around 45% of the sample stated that they view these innovative foods as important to facilitating a sustainable and healthy diet, while around 33% were neutral. This mixture of feelings suggests that while algae are perceived as potentially beneficial, their perception in a sustainable and healthy transition remains unclear.

Figure 20: Responses on the perception if algae-based foods facilitate a sustainable and healthy dietary transition.

5.2 Economic, Environmental, and Social Sustainability of Algae-Based Foods

When asked about the importance of algae-based foods in contributing to social, economic, and environmental sustainability (Figure 21), most respondents gave positive evaluations of their potential role. Over 50% of the respondents recognised the economic value of algae-based foods as a market opportunity for farmers and food producers. In terms of environmental sustainability, the respondents viewed algae as particularly promising because they are locally sourced and seasonal. Regarding social sustainability, approximately 52% of respondents emphasised the importance of algae-based foods for supporting local communities and small-scale producers.

Figure 21: Responses on the perception of the role of algae-based foods in the social, environmental and economic sustainability among the interviewees.

5.3 Trust in Algae

The respondents were asked to indicate their level of trust in algae-based foods (Figure 22). A significant portion (30–40%) of respondents reported feeling neutral, suggesting that they neither trust nor distrust these foods. On the other hand, a significant proportion of respondents (approximately 40%) trust algae-based foods, particularly regarding algae production, label transparency, and the quality of ingredients. Figure 23 shows that respondents in Germany and Norway, in particular, had the highest level of trust in new foods containing algae. In contrast, Lithuanian respondents had the lowest level of confidence among the countries surveyed.

Figure 22: Responses about the level of trust towards algae-based foods in the 7 EU countries.

Figure 23: Responses on how the consumer trust in algae-based foods vary by country, considering both production processes and producers.

Additionally, the respondents from the seven Northern and Eastern EU countries were asked to evaluate their level of trust in information resources regarding algae-based foods (Figure 24). Approximately 58% stated that they trust information about those innovative foods from the World Health Organisation (WHO), with similar percentages (around 50%) for government websites and search engines (e.g. Google). The least trustworthy source of information was felt to be social media (e.g. Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, TikTok).

Figure 24: Responses to what extent consumers trust various sources of information on algae-based foods.

5.4 Barriers to Consumption of Algae-Based Foods

The respondents were presented with 20 statements regarding possible barriers to the consumption of algae-based foods. Figure 25 is a heatmap showing the average agreement scores (on a Likert scale from 1 to 7) for a range of perceived barriers to consuming algae-based foods, segmented by dietary lifestyle: omnivore, flexitarian, pescetarian, vegetarian, and vegan.

Omnivores were found to report more barriers to the consumption of plant-based foods containing algae than those following plant-rich dietary lifestyles. Among these barriers, five stood out as the most significant, based on high average agreement scores (mostly rated five across dietary groups):

1. "Plant-based foods and snacks containing algae are not available when I eat out" – Rated five by all dietary groups, indicating widespread concern about availability.
2. "I need more information about algae-based foods" – Also rated five by all groups, highlighting a significant knowledge gap as a key barrier to acceptance.
3. "The algae-based food products I would need are not available where I shop or eat out" – Rated five by all omnivores, flexitarians, vegetarians, and vegans, reinforcing the issue of limited market access.
4. "Algae-based foods are not affordable" – Rated five across all groups, suggesting that cost is a universal barrier, even among those already engaged in plant-based diets.
5. "There is not enough choice in algae-based foods when I eat out" – Consistently rated 5, pointing to a lack of variety as a perceived market limitation.

Descriptive Statistics	Omnivore	Flexitarian	Pescetarian	Vegetarian	Vegan
There is not enough protein in algae-based foods.	4	4	4	4	4
There is not enough iron in algae-based foods.	4	4	4	4	4
I would be worried about my health (e.g., vit. B12, calcium)	5	4	4	4	4
I would get indigestion, bloating, gas, or flatulence when eating algae-based foods.	4	4	4	4	4
I wouldn't get enough energy or strength from algae-based foods.	4	4	4	4	3
I would need to eat a large quantity of algae-based foods to feel full.	5	4	4	4	4
I think humans are meant to eat lots of animal-based meat.	5	3	3	3	3
Algae-based foods would not be tasty enough.	5	4	4	4	3
Algae-based foods look too unusual.	5	4	4	4	4
Algae-based foods are inconvenient.	4	4	4	4	4
I do not enjoy eating algae-based foods.	4	4	4	4	4
Algae-based foods do not look appetizing or appealing.	5	4	4	4	4
I don't want to change my eating habits or routine.	5	4	4	4	4
My family/partner won't eat algae-based foods.	5	4	4	4	4
Algae-based foods are not safe.	4	4	4	4	3
There is not enough choice in algae-based foods products when I eat out.	5	5	5	5	5
Algae-based foods or snacks are not available when I eat out.	5	5	5	5	5
I need more information about algae-based foods.	5	5	5	5	5
The algae-based foods I would need are not available where I shop or eat out.	5	5	5	5	5
Algae-based foods are not affordable.	5	5	5	5	5

Figure 25: Responses on the barriers towards the consumption of algae-based foods.

5.5 Intentions Regarding Algae-Based Alternatives

When asked about their willingness to consume algae-based foods (Figure 26), most respondents (57%) expressed a positive attitude toward consuming these innovative foods. They were also asked to evaluate their likelihood of trying algae-based meat, fish, and egg alternatives. More than 50% of the total sample were very

positive about trying these, with around 56% willing to try the meat alternative; for the fish alternative, this was 54%, and for the egg alternative 50%. Despite most respondents being willing to try them, a notable proportion of respondents, mainly for the egg alternatives (32%), were reluctant to try these foods. This suggests that while algae-based foods are not yet mainstream, there is a promising market opportunity.

Figure 26: Responses on the willingness to consume algae-based foods.

Figure 27: Responses on the likelihood to try algae-based alternatives to meat, eggs, or fish.

5.6 Factors Influencing the Purchase of Algae-Based Foods

Consumers consider multiple factors when purchasing and consuming ASF analogues containing algae. As shown in Figure 28, most (62%) of the respondents identified that ASFs having a better taste than plant-based alternatives was a key driver of their behaviour, along with ease of access to nutritional information, greater market availability, and ease of preparation of the former. These findings confirm that taste and availability are critical factors influencing consumer choices. Therefore, the market must prioritise strategies that enhance sensory appeal and ensure product accessibility to facilitate broader adoption of algae-based foods.

Figure 28: Responses on the factors encouraging to purchase and consume algae-based foods.

5.7 Algae Percentage in Food Alternatives

Figure 29 shows that the respondents were generally more willing to try algae-based foods, such as fish, egg, and meat analogues, if the algae content of such foods does not exceed 10%. This indicates that while Northern Europeans are relatively interested in trying these foods, algae should be used initially as a complementary ingredient, rather than the main one, to facilitate consumer acceptance.

Figure 29A–C: Responses on the preference of algae works best in a meat, egg, and fish alternative.

5.8 Sensory Preferences Regarding Imagined Algae-Based Alternatives

The respondents were asked to indicate their preferences regarding key sensory characteristics concerning three foods containing algae, on which LOCALITY researchers are focused: an egg, a meat, and a fish alternative. Multiple attributes were presented for each sensory modality – appearance, odour, taste/flavour, texture/mouthfeel – and the findings are presented in a series of charts for each product, which will feed the tasks on food products development, marketing strategies, and further research into maximising consumer appeal and acceptance of alternative proteins.

As is illustrated in Figure 30, consumer sensory expectations regarding an ideal algae-based egg alternative reveal distinct preferences across key dimensions. Regarding taste, the respondents expressed a preference for an "eggy" flavour, and an aversion to matcha/green and bitter notes. Regarding texture, tenderness was positively evaluated, whereas fatty or fluid sensations were generally disliked. In terms of appearance, the respondents expect a light-yellow colour like traditional eggs and reject any foamy visual characteristics. Finally, concerning odour, attributes such as creaminess and roasted aromas were preferred, while a sweet aroma was considered the least desirable.

Figure 30: Responses on the sensory expectations for an ideal algae-based egg alternative.

Figure 31 shows that the respondents expect an ideal algae-based meat alternative to taste salty and beef-like, while vegetable-like flavours were negatively perceived. For texture, the respondents favoured a uniform and tender consistency, explicitly rejecting firmness, which they perceived as unnatural or unappealing. Regarding appearance, a brown colour was preferred, likely due to its association with cooked meat, whereas green was viewed negatively. Finally, a distinctly meaty aroma was felt to be essential for the respondents to have an experience similar to traditional meat, and to enhance overall product acceptance.

The respondents expressed distinct sensory expectations regarding an ideal algae-based fish alternative (Figure 32). Regarding taste, fresh fish, marine, and salty profiles were the most positively evaluated, whereas bitter, acidic, and ammonia flavours were firmly rejected. Regarding texture, attributes such as soft, crisp, and firm were preferred, while a fatty mouthfeel was considered undesirable. For appearance, a bright product was seen as ideal, while elastic traits were viewed negatively. In terms of odour, freshness was felt to be essential to meeting expectations, while rancid or sour notes were not well perceived.

Figure 31: Responses on the sensory expectations for an ideal algae-based meat alternative.

What are the sensory expectations for an ideal algae-based fish alternative?

Figure 32: Responses on the sensory expectations for an ideal algae-based fish alternative.

6 Preferences Regarding Alternative Proteins

The respondents were asked to rank alternative proteins in terms of which they would most like to see or purchase. The alternative proteins selected were:

- Plant-based fermented proteins (based on cereals, pulses, grains)
- Cultivated proteins (e.g., cultivated meat, cultivated dairy, etc.)
- Fungi-based proteins (e.g., mushrooms, mycelium, yeast)
- Algae-based proteins (made from micro and/or macroalgae)
- Insect-based proteins
- Plant-based proteins (e.g., extruded proteins from grains such as lentils or soya)

The most preferred proteins among the respondents from the seven Northern and Eastern EU countries were fermented plant-based ones, as illustrated in Figure 33. Cultivated proteins were the second most preferred type of alternative protein, with 23% of respondents selecting them, followed by extruded plant-based proteins (18%). Fungi-based and algae-based proteins were less preferred, at 14% and 8%, respectively. The least preferred protein source was insect-based, with only 3% of respondents choosing it as their favourite source of alternative protein. While algae exhibited a relatively low baseline preference, this highlights a strategic opportunity for targeted communication and market repositioning. Consumer reluctance may be caused by a lack of familiarity, poor taste associations, or insufficient information – barriers identified in this study. Educational campaigns emphasising the nutritional benefits, environmental sustainability, and versatility of algae, coupled with culinary innovation to improve taste and texture, could facilitate consumer acceptance of algae-based foods over time.

Figure 33: Responses on preferred alternative proteins in the 7 EU countries.

When the respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with various attitudinal statements relating to their perceptions of the healthiness, safety, and taste of alternative proteins (Figure 34), a notable portion of the sample evaluated these innovative foods positively. Nearly half of the respondents identified healthiness and safety as the main positive attributes of plant-based fermented foods. Similarly, for fungi-based proteins, 54% of the participants rated healthiness as the most critical aspect. A considerable share of the sample also perceived cultivated proteins positively. However, many of the respondents expressed neutral attitudes, indicating potential uncertainty or ambivalence regarding cultivated proteins.

Approximately 60% of the participants considered extruded plant proteins to be safe, showing a relatively high level of consumer trust in this processing method. Conversely, insect-based proteins were rated consistently low across all attitude dimensions. A notable share of the respondents expressed negative perceptions, 30–33% felt neutral, and a small minority (20% approx.) rated these products positively.

Interestingly, although algae-based proteins ranked low in overall preference (Figure 33), they received a more favourable attitudinal evaluation. About 50% of the respondents perceived algae-based foods to be healthy, with a similar proportion also considering them safe.

Figure 34: Responses on the attitudes towards alternative proteins in the 7 EU countries.

The respondents were asked to evaluate the importance of alternative proteins for the future of the food system (Figure 35). Extruded plant-based proteins were evaluated most positively in this regard, followed by fungi- and algae-based proteins (54% and 53%, respectively, of participants seeing them as important to the future of the food system). Cultivated and fermented foods were also positively evaluated, with half of the sample recognising the key role of these foods in the food system. Interestingly, despite the current EU food agenda promoting the importance of insect protein for the future of the European food system, consumer data clearly indicates a low level of positive agreement with this.

The data indicate that the respondents from seven Northern EU countries see alternative proteins as being central to the future of the food system, reflecting a growing awareness of the role of these foods in driving a

more sustainable and healthy dietary transition. This highlights the strong potential for aligning innovation with public values in shaping future food policies.

Figure 35: Responses on the importance of alternative proteins for the future of food.

7 Policy Propositions Towards Plant-Based Transition

Several food policy schemes have been implemented in the EU to facilitate a transition towards sustainable and healthy food systems. The respondents from the seven Northern and Eastern EU countries were asked to evaluate which policies and actions could facilitate a European plant-based transition (Figure 36). Education, to provide the necessary information about healthy eating in schools, was identified as the most important strategy for the transition, with 70% of the respondents agreeing. Another key strategy identified is supporting farmers who seek to transition their production to plant-based farming. This involves recognising the structural changes that are needed in agricultural systems to meet sustainability goals and reducing reliance on animal agriculture. Around 42% of the respondents agreed with the idea of reducing subsidies for meat and dairy producers (large industrial facilities), suggesting a potential disconnect between consumers' environmental values and willingness to support policy changes that might affect product prices.

Figure 36: Responses on the perceptions of policymakers' actions in supporting a plant-based transition.

8 Consumer Preferences Regarding Future Sources of Textile Dye

As part of Task 7 of the LOCALITY project, which aims to develop resource-efficient textile processing methods for dyeing using algae additives, the following section focuses on gathering information about respondents' preferences for future textile dye sources derived from alternative resources, including algae. In Figure 37, respondents were asked to evaluate their preferences regarding future sources of textile dye with lower environmental impact and better alignment with broader sustainability goals. Roughly 73% of respondents felt that blueberry was the best source of future dye. Algae were also positively evaluated, with more than 60% of respondents favouring their usage. Lice were the dye source that the respondents least preferred. When they were asked to evaluate product applications for algae-based alternatives concerning clothing (Figure 38), most were in favour of the use of algae in the production of dirt-repellent and waterproof fabrics.

Figure 37: Responses on the consumer preferences for future textile dye sources.

This study shows that consumers in Northern European countries are increasingly receptive to the adoption of alternative dye sources for use in the textile sector, especially algae, demonstrating a strong preference for innovations that can reduce environmental impact. This suggests a positive shift in consumer behaviour that could significantly accelerate the transition towards environmentally friendly textile dye sources.

Figure 38: Responses on the preferred product applications for algae-based alternatives in clothing.

9 Discussion

The LOCALITY survey findings highlight evolving dietary patterns in Northern and Eastern Europe, where animal-based diets are still predominant but flexitarianism is increasing, particularly in Germany. Despite national recommendations to reduce animal-based foods, meat and dairy remain central, although a notable segment of respondents intend to reduce meat consumption within six months. These dietary trends align with findings from other EU projects, particularly with SmartProtein and HealthFerm, which also report the predominance of animal-based diets across Europe alongside rising numbers of flexitarian consumers, reflecting growing awareness of sustainability and health among EU consumers. Consumer openness to alternative proteins, especially with algae-based foods, is emerging but cautious. Health and sustainability are recognised as necessary, yet taste, texture, and affordability remain the main drivers of food choice. The findings show that Northern and Eastern EU consumers are most willing to try algae-based foods when algae are used at low inclusion levels (~10%) and incorporated into familiar food formats, highlighting the need for gradual integration. Trust and familiarity vary regionally, with higher acceptance in Germany and Norway, possibly reflecting Germany's openness to novel food innovations and Norway's long tradition of seaweed cultivation, suggesting that clear communication and transparency about production and health benefits are key issues to consider. Regarding the sensory expectations, the findings show that algae-based fish and meat alternatives are more favourably perceived than egg alternatives, emphasising the importance of aligning products with familiar and appealing sensory profiles to foster consumer acceptance.

Overall, the findings suggest that algae-based foods could play a meaningful role in Northern and Eastern Europe's alternative protein landscape if introduced gradually with clear communication and attention to consumer sensory expectations, underling the need for targeted communication strategies by the LOCALITY consortium to foster consumer interest and position these foods as a key component of a sustainable and healthy food transition across Europe.

10 About the Study

For the purposes of the study, Umeå University, together with partners of the LOCALITY Consortium, produced and distributed a questionnaire to explore the attitudes and behaviour of respondents concerning algae-based foods, and the market opportunities relating to these. The questionnaire included socio-demographic information that facilitated segmenting and statistical modelling. This report is based on the first wave of questionnaires, which were distributed between November 2024 and December 2024 to SE, DE, FI, EE, LT, NO, and PL. The questionnaire covered socio-demographic characteristics (sex, age, locality of residence, education level, financial situation, and dietary habits) to ensure representativeness and sufficient statistical power, and to further control for known confounding. The survey was completed by respondents who were recruited by Enkätfabriken AB, with a total of 5,250 participants over the age of 18, at least 750 respondents per country, and equal numbers of females and males (50% each approx.) across five age groups: 18–30, 30–40, 40–50, 50–60, and 60+. The participants provided information about their eating habits, although only self-identified flexitarians and omnivores were asked about their consumption of meat and intentions regarding reducing or increasing their current consumption levels.

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